

Classroom-Based assessment practices and assessment literacy in Moroccan EFL high schools

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Abstract

Classroom-Based Assessment (CBA) is a multifaceted process that has a direct bearing on various dimensions of learning and teaching. The present study investigates Moroccan EFL teachers' CBA practices and the extent to which teachers' assessment literacy enhances these practices. Through a concurrent triangulation mixed-methods approach, the data were collected using online self-report questionnaires administered to 225 EFL teacher participants, semi-structured interviews conducted on seven EFL teacher participants and document analysis based on tests and materials shared by twelve EFL teacher participants. The study yielded several key findings. First, summative and objective written quizzes and tests are frequently used as formal CBA procedures to assess language components, reading and writing. As for the informal CBA procedures, teacher observation is frequently used, while performance-based assessments are sometimes used as fluency-oriented activities. Second, the study provides important information about teachers' assessment literacy. EFL teachers receive minimal CBA training, primarily emphasizing test design during pre-service training, with limited Continuous

Professional Development (CPD). The findings have implications for curriculum design, teacher training, teaching and research, emphasizing the necessity of enhancing CBA practices through teacher education programs and CPD activities.

Keywords: CBA practices, procedures, language components, skills, considerations, constraints, assessment literacy

0. Introduction

Classroom-Based Assessment (CBA) is considered one of the most influential forms of educational measurement. As a mode of “assessment internal to the classroom and managed by the teacher” (Turner, 2012, p. 63), it represents a dynamic and systematic process inherent in the instructional design of language teaching and learning. Informal and formal procedures, in this regard, provide feedback meant for summative and formative purposes or some combination of both through the implementation of a wide range of assessment tools, including tests and quizzes. Therefore, to improve educational quality, it is necessary to use well-designed empirical studies to provide the foundation for enhancing CBA effectiveness (McMillan, 2013) and account for the significant gap in the CBA literature between contemporary theories of assessment culture, principles, knowledge, and skills on one hand, and their practical application in real educational contexts on the other (Inbar-Lourie, 2017). Accordingly, examining CBA practices in the EFL context is a worthwhile endeavor.

Assessment Literacy (AL) enhances the effectiveness of CBA practices, especially for formative decision-making. CBA literacy should, therefore, not be limited only to the interpretation of summative test scores. This posits that CBA practices are fundamentally meant to inform learners about their progress, identify their gaps in knowledge, and help them overcome these issues by collaboratively devising remedial work to overcome their weaknesses. Despite this, very few teacher education programs equip teachers with a deep understanding of the relationship between CBA practices and student learning progress (Bailey & Durán, 2019; Broadfoot et al., 2001). The Moroccan EFL context is no exception. Benzehaf (2017) argues that a lack of assessment literacy is more likely to be detrimental to students. Moreover, teachers’ perceptions and practical applications of assessment literacy influence their modes of teaching and assessment (Hakim, 2015). Therefore, it is worthwhile to shed light on teachers’ assessment literacy to understand CBA practices.

Building on this background, the present study aims to examine the prevailing CBA practices and the role of AL in enhancing these practices using quantitative (online self-report questionnaires) and qualitative (semi-

structured interviews and document analysis) instruments simultaneously. As an overall aim, this study seeks to contribute to the scholarly literature on CBA practices and literacy in the Moroccan EFL context, document the actual CBA practices, account for their widespread uses and purposes, and examine whether EFL teachers are trained to implement effective CBA practices. To achieve these objectives, the following questions have been formulated:

RQ1: What are the predominant CBA practices in Moroccan EFL high schools?

RQ2: To what extent does teachers' AL contribute to the enhancement of their CBA practices in Moroccan EFL high schools?

1. Literature Review

1.1 CBA: Definitions and Concerns

CBA, as defined by McMillan (2013), is considered “a broad and evolving conceptualization of a process that teachers and students use in collecting, evaluating, and using evidence of student learning for a variety of purposes” (p. 4). Kane and Wools (2019) view it as involving the collection of information from various sources meant for different purposes, including formative decision-making. Lewkowicz and Leung (2021) emphasize the formative role of CBA, which encompasses “any teacher-led classroom activity designed to find out about students' performance on curriculum tasks that would yield information regarding their understanding as well as their need for further support and scaffolding concerning their situated learning needs” (p. 48). In light of this, feedback, scaffolding, monitoring of students' progress and adjustment of these to learning needs and contexts exist at the core of CBA effective implementation.

In addition to informing pedagogical practices and enhancing learners' cognitive and affective development, CBA serves another critical dimension. This is related to the impact that traditional testing has on teaching and learning, on tailoring curriculum objectives to serve testing purposes, hence resulting in identifying a priori all learning experiences and teaching activities (Hamp-Lyons, 2007). It also assures more curricular alignment of assessment procedures with objectives, content, methodology and learners' needs. Besides its being embedded in a specific curricular architecture, CBA is locally contextualized and primarily learning-oriented. By triangulating data collection, teachers and, presumably, students gain rich and consistent input from multiple sources, such as tests and other alternative assessments. This also allows for the improvement of learners' higher-order thinking skills and the accommodation of their different needs and styles through differentiated assessment.

Oriented towards learning, CBA employs diverse assessment procedures and tasks on multiple occasions, which results in more fairness and transparency as opposed to focusing solely on pen-and-paper tests and product measurement. In this regard, alternative assessment includes more constructive assessment strategies than standard external items (Shohamy, 2017). This new perspective has “led to the use of a broader range of assessment procedures, and these procedures take into account the nature of language ability, the characteristics of test takers and tasks, and the context of language use” (Stoynoff, 2012, p. 527). The employment of various procedures, such as portfolios, presentations, teacher observations and peer and self-assessment, and the systematic implementation of assessment is what reversed the psychometric tradition advocating for the quantification of students’ abilities to a more comprehensive and inclusive approach that situates the learner at the center of the whole instructional enterprise.

1.2 The Role of AL in CBA

In language classrooms, AL is a prerequisite for teachers to increase the efficiency of their CBA practices. Inbar-Lourie (2017) defined Language Assessment Literacy (LAL) as “the knowledge, skills and principles that stakeholders involved in assessment activities are required to master to perform assessment tasks” (p. 257). AL, in this regard, refers to conceptual, practical and technical dimensions as well as institutional and social dimensions relating to washback, ethics and professionalism (Davies, 2008, as cited in Fulcher, 2012). It is clear that AL is not restricted only to the interpretation of test scores (Bailey & Durán, 2019) but encompasses other broader concerns.

Despite the significance of AL for language teachers, “nearly all researchers evaluating teacher assessment literacy lament the limited knowledge and skills of teachers in the areas of item development, test design, administration, scoring and reporting” (Rodriguez & Haladyna, 2013, p. 294). Other researchers in the Moroccan EFL context tend to corroborate this state of affairs (Ghaicha, 2016; Ghaicha & Oufela, 2021). This limited knowledge about language assessment can be attributed to a lack of assessment-related materials and course books that are not within practitioners’ reach and/or addressed to non-professionals in terms of terminology and discourse (Fulcher, 2012), not to mention other factors related to perceptions, work overload, lack of experience, lack of pre-service training and scarcity of continuous professional development opportunities.

1.3 CBA Practices and Literacy in the Moroccan EFL context: An empirical caveat

The available empirical research findings on CBA practices in the Moroccan EFL context indicate that CBA is underdeveloped and warrants significant attention from researchers and educators. Based on a review of a sample of studies, CBA is approached from a measurement perspective and perceived as a means to evaluate students' degree of mastery of English using mostly activities, such as: true/false, fill in the blanks, matching and sentence completion compared to any other alternative assessment methods (Mamad & Vigh, 2021). Besides, alternative assessment procedures are also perceived as less effective in communicating information; hence, their implementation is limited only to role plays, oral presentations, and mini-projects (Babni, 2019). More than this, surprisingly, self-assessment is rarely used in EFL classrooms (Ghaicha & Oufela, 2021). Therefore, it is evident that CBA is perceived as an end in itself, essentially as a set of summative and objective written procedures and items to measure students' achievement.

The prevailing assessment system necessitates a change at the levels of organization, design, and implementation, which has been an enduring issue (Ouakrime, 2000). Presumably, two main reasons call for a change in the current CBA practices. These include its focus on recalling information, hence providing limited feedback to students, and the use of its information and results mainly for administrative purposes. For this reason, CBA feedback is considered "weak" as a pedagogical resource (World Bank Group, 2015). Given the current prevailing CBA practices, Ghaicha (2016) argues that CBA is either not adequately understood or not implemented based on an educational framework. However, the level(s) where change is required and the specific interventions needed to account for the current CBA limitations and challenges have yet to be determined on sufficient empirical grounds.

EFL teachers' ineffective CBA practices can be attributed to the compelling challenges, including the inadequacy of the content covered in teacher education and training programs (Babni, 2019; Ghaicha & Omarkaly, 2018; Ghaicha & Oufela, 2021). This is all the more important when considering the exam culture prevalent in the Moroccan educational system, resulting in teachers' reluctance to adopt formative assessment tools and a lack of knowledge, skills and interest to engage in professional development. Therefore, it is worth allotting priority to training pre-service and in-service teachers on effective assessment practices (Bouziane, 2017; Hakim, 2015), with centering CPD programs on the design of assessment rubrics, grading

criteria and use of assessment for feedback purposes (Benzehaf, 2017). The present empirical contribution is therefore meant to further examine this area.

2. Methods

2.1 Research Design and Instruments

This study employs a mixed methods approach, a pragmatic worldview with a concurrent triangulation strategy, which involves the collection of quantitative and qualitative data and merging them in the discussion to provide a more well-rounded analysis of the research problem (Creswell, 2009). To collect quantitative data, this study used an online self-report questionnaire. It consists of three main sections: Demographic Information, CBA Practices and Assessment Literacy (AL). The questionnaire targets the major constructs of this study, namely: CBA procedures, The Assessment of the Language Components and Skills, CBA Considerations and Constraints, Participation in Assessment Training and Sources of AL. Besides, it employs various item formats. These include multiple-choice items, multiple-response items, and Likert scales, along with spaces for additional comments.

Concerning the qualitative data, semi-structured interviews accompanied by an interview guide were utilized to provide guidance to the interviewees and to allow them to elaborate on certain issues and to follow up on interesting developments (Dörnyei, 2007). The interviews were conducted in around 30 minutes. Additionally, document analysis was employed, which involves the examination and interpretation of the participants' documents to "elicit meaning, gain understanding, and develop empirical knowledge (Corbin & Strauss, 2008; see also Rapley, 2007)" (Bowen, 2009, p. 27). These documents include portfolios where teachers collect examples of their CBA-related documents, providing a less expensive measure of actual practice than a self-report of practice (Randel & Clark, 2013).

2.2 Validity and Reliability Issues

In this study, the triangulation of the research instruments is meant to provide "a confluence of evidence that breeds credibility" (Eisner, 1991, p. 110, as cited in Bowen, 2009), help avoid bias and assure more validity of the findings. Moreover, the questionnaire, the interview guide and the document request letter were carefully edited by the authors and shared with three EFL teachers for feedback. Accordingly, the necessary modifications were made to ensure the clarity of instructions and questions. Furthermore, the reliability of the Likert scales used to measure the frequency of "CBA Procedures" and "The Assessment of the Language Skills and Components" was confirmed with Cronbach's Alpha values of 0.78 and 0.72, respectively.

2.3 Participants

The participants in this study were Moroccan EFL high school teachers. First, 225 EFL teachers completed an online self-report questionnaire based on accidental sampling; about 35.6% of them teach an average class size between 15 to 20 students, while 23.6% teach an average class size between 35 and 40 students. Second, seven EFL teachers voluntarily participated in the semi-structured interviews. Their teaching experience was between one year and twenty-four years. Most of them teach between 18 to 21 hours per week. Third, twelve EFL teacher participants took part in document analysis. Their teaching hours were between fifteen to twenty hours a week.

2.4 Ethical Considerations

All the participants in this study were informed about the purpose and the completion time of each data collection instrument. Besides, the anonymity and confidentiality of their responses were guaranteed in advance. To illustrate, participants in the semi-structured interviews responded to an informed consent sent online in a Google Form® before the interview; permission to audio record the interviews was also requested. Besides, a copy of the interview transcript was sent later to each participant to confirm their responses. In document analysis, each participant received an online formal request letter to voluntarily share their CBA practices-related documents.

2.5 Data Collection Procedure and Analysis

The questionnaire was disseminated to the participants via Google Forms® due to its feasibility in accessing more participants in a short time. Subsequently, the data collected was coded using Microsoft Excel (2009) and analyzed using SPSS 26.0 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY). Different statistical measures were applied. The percentages revealed through frequency charts, graphs, and contingency tables generated quantitative data.

To collect semi-structured interview data, participants were sent Google Forms® to fill in their background information as well as express their informed consent. The meetings were then conducted using Google Meet and were recorded using the “Vmaker” application. Subsequently, each interviewee’s responses were transcribed into Word documents. The data collected was subjected to thematic analysis and interpretation.

Concerning document analysis, as mentioned above, a request letter was sent to EFL teachers. In response to this letter, EFL teachers shared folders containing scanned or PDF documents related to CBA practices. The received documents were divided into categories depending on their content before subjecting them to content analysis.

3. Results

3.1 Questionnaire Data Analysis

3.1.1 CBA Practices in Moroccan EFL High Schools

Regarding CBA procedures, Table 1 demonstrates that the most frequent CBA procedures used in EFL classrooms are formal written procedures. Specifically, 42.9% of EFL teachers always use language tests and global exams, 40.3% always use objective assessments (e.g., multiple choice), and 35.8% always use timed quizzes on separate skills and language components. On the other hand, concerning informal CBA procedures, 31.4% always use observation. EFL teachers sometimes use other informal CBA procedures; they include the following: performance-based assessment (e.g., project work) (42%), oral presentations (40.7%), peer assessment (38.9%), essay-type questions (35.8%) and oral interviews (33.2%), respectively. However, almost the same percentage of EFL teachers rarely use students' assessment journals and self-assessments accompanied by a checklist (31.9% and 31% respectively), while 47% never use portfolios/ e-portfolios and students' assessment journals.

Table 1. The frequency of using formal and informal CBA procedures.

Procedures / Frequency	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Usually	Always
Performance-based assessments (e.g., project work, role-plays).	4.4	23.0	42.0	20.8	9.3
Timed quizzes on separate skills and language components.	0.4	7.5	20.4	35.4	35.8
Students' journals	47.3	31.9	13.7	4.9	1.8
Assessments that measure how well students remember information.	6.2	15.5	38.5	27.0	12.4
Oral presentations	11.5	25.2	40.7	18.6	3.5

Essay-type questions (e.g. writing essays)	11.1	22.6	35.8	24.3	5.8
Assessment tasks aligned with the English national exam content and rubrics (e.g. samples of the English national exam)	8.4	12.4	22.6	30.5	25.7
Homework and other course-related assignments	1.8	9.7	27.4	28.8	31.9
Objective assessments (e.g., multiple-choice, matching, short answer exercises)	0.4	5.8	21.7	31.4	40.3
Peer assessment (e.g. students correcting each other's work).	12.4	23.5	38.9	18.6	6.2
Language tests and global exams.	1.8	5.3	19.9	29.6	42.9
Self-assessment accompanied by a checklist.	26.1	31.0	26.5	12.4	3.5
Portfolios /e-portfolios	47.8	26.5	15.5	7.5	2.2
Teacher's observation	9.3	16.8	24.8	17.3	31.4
Oral exams/interviews	22.2	27.4	33.2	31.1	5.3

Concerning the CBA of language skills and components, Figure 1 shows that the majority of EFL teachers frequently assess language components compared to the four skills, though with slightly varying degrees: grammar (62.8%), vocabulary (59.7%), and functions (57.1%).

The Frequency of Assessing Language Skills and Components

Figure 1. The frequency of assessing language skills and components

Additionally, a notable portion of EFL teachers usually assess vocabulary (31%), functions (30.5%), and grammar (29.6%). As for the four skills, 33.6% of the participants always assess reading, while 31.4% revealed that this happens usually. Besides, 36.3% of EFL teachers usually assess writing, while 28.3% sometimes do. Regarding listening and speaking, 35% rarely assess listening, 27.9% assess it sometimes, and 25.2% never do. Meanwhile, 34.1% sometimes assess speaking, and only 25.2% usually do.

Pertaining to CBA considerations, Table 2 demonstrates that 95.9% of EFL teachers consider course objectives when opting for a CBA procedure, with over 80% privileging its practical aspects, including efficiency, cost and ease of use. Besides, more than 70% reference the Pedagogical Guidelines (2007) and the Baccalaureate Specifications (2014), while only 50.9% consider the Ministerial Circular number 142-07.

Table 2. CBA considerations

	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Per cent	
Course objectives	213	25.3%	95.9%

Practicality (efficiency in time, cost/ease in administration and scoring)	189	22.4%	85.1%
Pedagogical Guidelines for Teaching English (2007)	168	20.0%	75.7%
Baccalaureate Specifications (2014)	159	18.9%	71.6%
The Ministerial Circular N° 142-07 (2007)	113	13.4%	50.9%

As for CBA constraints, Table 3 indicates that the majority of EFL teachers commonly encounter challenges related to insufficient time and students' prioritization of grades. Specifically, when implementing CBA procedures, 86% of EFL teachers experience time constraints, 76% emphasize students' preoccupation with grades and 68% encounter issues related to students' lack of engagement and motivation. Emphasis on teaching to the test is another major constraint, as highlighted by 65% of the participants.

Table 3. CBA constraints

	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Per cent	
Insufficient Time	192	23.0%	86.9%
Students only value what is marked (e.g. tests).	170	20.4%	76.9%
Lack of students' motivation and involvement.	151	18.1%	68.3%
Emphasis on teaching to the test (e.g. national exam)	145	17.4%	65.6%
Lack of collaborative work among teachers	97	11.6%	43.9%
Poor assessment knowledge and Lack of CPD activities	80	9.6%	36.2%

3.1.2 Teachers' AL in Moroccan EFL High Schools

Initiating with training, Figure 2 indicates that only 42.5% of EFL teachers have participated in training on assessment while 57.1 % have never participated in any assessment training.

Figure 2. Teachers' participation in assessment training

For developing AL, Table 4 reveals that the majority of EFL teachers (74.7%) enhance their assessment knowledge and skills through practical experimentation with CBA. Conversely, only 46.2% completed a course in which assessment was a component. Additionally, 60.9% read books and other sources to update their assessment knowledge, while 47.1% attend meetings or workshops suggested by their supervisors.

Table 4. Teachers' sources for developing their AL

	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Per cent	
I develop my assessment knowledge and skills from my classroom practices (e.g. trial and error).	168	26.0%	74.7%
I read books and other sources to update my knowledge of assessment.	137	21.2%	60.9%
I have attended the meeting(s)/ workshops held by my supervisor on assessment.	106	16.4%	47.1%
I completed a course in which assessment was part of the course.	104	16.1%	46.2%
I participated in online webinars on assessment.	66	10.2%	29.3%

I completed a full course on assessment.	66	10.2%	29.3%
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3.2 Semi-Structured Interview Data Analysis

3.1.2 CBA Practices in Moroccan EFL High Schools

The interviews revealed that EFL teachers predominantly employ formal written CBA procedures, alongside informal performance-based assessment activities for two main purposes. First, nearly all EFL teachers use two formal written quizzes and one global test each semester to document students' achievement for grading purposes as mandated by the school administration. Second, the majority integrate informal performance-based assessment activities (e.g., role plays) to increase fluency-oriented practice opportunities targeting language components. This is usually done by integrating speaking or writing skills into meaningful activities.

Some EFL teachers indicated that they systematically document students' performance in informal performance-based assessment activities. For instance, some use grids to track student participation and homework completion, as one teacher mentioned, "I use a grid with marks, where I grade students according to their participation, homework and assignments". Furthermore, some EFL teachers consider both in-class and out-of-class performance factors, such as class participation, homework and projects, when they assign grades to students at the end of the semester. However, EFL teachers demonstrated variability in the informal performance-based assessment procedures they opt for, the performance factors they consider when documenting students' in and out-of-class performance and the degree of organization they keep during the recording process.

Nearly all EFL teachers interviewed prioritize students' proficiency levels when implementing CBA procedures. One of the participants highlighted the need for varied procedures to accommodate students' differences in English proficiency by stating that "students come from different contexts; they used to have different teachers, so you have to vary the tasks in terms of easiness or challenge or simplicity". Additionally, the majority of teachers align their written tests and items with the Baccalaureate Specifications (2014) to ensure students' familiarity with the rubrics or instructions. Other considerations mentioned include learning objectives and time constraints (e.g., practicality). Moreover, some EFL teachers integrate informal performance-based procedures outlined in the English Pedagogical Guidelines (2007) into their CBA practices, such as role-plays and projects.

The majority of the interviewees expressed concerns about the limited time available to use informal in-class performance-based assessment tasks. For instance, one of the participants revealed that "time for consolidation, for free

practice, and assessment” can only be done, as he affirms, “at the expense of failing to finish the syllabus”. Therefore, syllabus overload, as confirmed by some participants, is another constraint that works against the adequate integration of the informal CBA procedures. Additionally, inadequate coverage of these procedures in the textbooks further constrains their integration, as one teacher remarked: “they are not provided in the textbook”. Besides, almost all the participants reported that their use of both the informal in-class and out-of-class continuous assessment activities is constrained by students’ lack of involvement and familiarity (e.g., lack of training) with these procedures.

The majority of EFL teachers interviewed opt for formal CBA procedures (e.g., written quizzes) to assess separate language components. They additionally assess students’ fluent use of these components by integrating informal performance-based assessment activities (e.g., role play) in the production stage of the lessons. As for the four skills, nearly all teachers assess reading formally; however, only a minority assess writing. Some attribute the omission of writing assessment to students’ limited practice opportunities, while others find it difficult to score writing tasks objectively. Furthermore, most of the interviewees do not formally assess speaking and listening. Additionally, others refrain from assessing speaking and listening formally due to time constraints and insufficient facilities.

3.1.3 Teachers’ AL in Moroccan EFL High Schools

The interview analysis demonstrated that EFL teachers receive limited pre-service and in-service training on assessment. Many indicated that their training as pre-service teachers was limited to a single part of a broader program focused mainly on test design and administration. Additionally, the CPD opportunities for assessment are notably lacking. Consequently, many teachers express a pressing need for more assessment training, especially emphasizing its significance for formative purposes. As one teacher emphasized: “as teachers, we should know how to use assessment effectively to help students develop in all areas and to learn for life”. Therefore, there is a need among EFL teachers for effective pre-service and in-service training programs on assessment practices, encompassing a wide range of assessment procedures to effectively monitor students’ learning progress.

3.2 Document Analysis

The documents shared by the participants consist of three categories: samples of formal written CBA procedures, grading lists for recording students’ performance data in the formal and informal CBA procedures and grids for regularly tracking students’ performance in the informal in-class and out-of-class assessment activities.

Written quizzes or tests are used as formal CBA procedures to assess students' achievement of language components, reading and writing. Written quizzes target language components separately, often using close-ended tasks, such as: "multiple-choice tasks", "matching exercises", and "fill in the blanks". Additionally, reading quizzes include reading texts accompanied by "true/false tasks" and "wh-questions", while writing quizzes incorporate tasks such as paragraph writing or short essays. Conversely, written tests may involve separate sections dedicated to reading and writing in addition to language component(s). Notably, formal written CBA procedures largely focus on language components. Furthermore, in some cases, EFL teachers administer multiple versions of a single written test or quiz (e.g., versions A and B) concurrently to students in the same class.

EFL teachers document students' performance in both formal and informal CBA procedures. In formal written quizzes and tests, students' achievements are recorded in a grading list, which is eventually submitted to the school administration. Besides, students' performance records include in-class and out-of-class performance-based assessments, graded holistically. These grades are assigned by teachers subjectively based on their impressions from unstructured class observations. Otherwise, grids are employed to track students' performance throughout the semester systematically. In brief, EFL teachers record students' performance in both formal and informal CBA procedures primarily for summative purposes, as mandated by the school administration.

4. Discussion

4.1 The Prevailing CBA Practices

Significant findings have transpired from the present study. With respect to the first research question about the prevailing CBA practices in Moroccan EFL high schools, it is revealed that CBA practices predominantly consist of formal and objective written procedures. These are meant to assess separate language components using tasks such as "multiple-choice" and "fill-in-the-blanks". This corroborates the findings yielded by Mamad and Vigh's (2021) study, which confirms the use of the same traditional assessment methods (e.g., fill-in-the-blanks) in the Moroccan context. It is apparent that CBA is approached as formal pen-and-paper tests to measure discrete linguistic points and often centers on recalling information (World Bank Group, 2015), disregarding the potential outcomes of alternative assessment procedures (Shohamy, 2017).

Informal CBA procedures are primarily used to assess the fluent use of language components. These procedures often involve activities such as role plays, oral presentations, peer assessments, essay-type questions and oral

interviews, despite the infrequent use of assessment journals and self-assessments. Some of these procedures, such as role plays, presentations, and mini-projects, partially align with alternative assessment procedures previously identified by Babni (2019). Furthermore, the findings reveal limited use of self-assessment. This aligns with Ghaicha and Oufela's findings (2021), which indicate that nearly one-third of the participants rarely and never incorporate self-assessment. Overall, the integration of alternative and performance-based assessment activities remains limited and scarce in the Moroccan EFL context.

Concerning the formal CBA of the four skills in the EFL context, it largely emphasizes the assessment of reading; writing comes next, while speaking and listening are entirely overlooked as the focus of the formal CBA. The analysis of the interview data reveals that the limited formal assessment of writing is justified by the dearth of practice opportunities students have and the difficulties associated with scoring writing objectively. As for the exclusion of speaking and listening from formal CBA procedures, it is attributed to constraints related to time and facilities. Hence, the current approach to CBA when it comes to the four skills is primarily viewed as a measurement instrument.

Based on the qualitative data analysis, it is self-evident that some EFL teachers record students' performance in the informal, in-class and out-of-class CBA procedures, albeit they are primarily intended for formative purposes. This practice supports the findings from the questionnaire, which emphasizes the prevalent use of observation as an informal CBA procedure. Conversely, there exists a noticeable lack of consistency in how these performance-based assessment activities are used, the factors considered when recording students' performance, and the level of systematicity in this recording process. Presumably, this inconsistency may stem from a lack of detailed official guidelines on CBA practices or a potential lack of CBA literacy among EFL teachers (Ghaicha, 2016).

Despite employing informal CBA procedures primarily for formative purposes, there is still a dearth of explicit criteria delineating performance levels. None of the interviewed EFL teachers mentioned using assessment criteria to provide students with descriptive feedback, even though some of them record students' performance in informal, in-class performance-based assessment activities using a grid. This neglect of assessment criteria may be attributed to EFL teachers' perceptions that alternative assessment procedures do not adequately reveal learners' proficiency levels (Babni, 2019). Consequently, employing alternative and performance-based activities with explicit performance criteria linked to specific and measurable learning goals

is necessary to provide formative feedback and foster students' involvement in CBA processes.

During CBA implementation, EFL teachers navigate various considerations. Initially, the quantitative and qualitative data analysis revealed that they prioritize aspects such as course objectives, the practicality of the CBA procedures, adherence to the English Pedagogical Guidelines (2007) and compliance with the Baccalaureate Specifications (2014). However, surprisingly, the ministerial circular (142-07) is overlooked, despite its relevance to CBA practices. The interview data analysis also demonstrated that teachers prioritize students' proficiency level, especially in mixed-ability classes, to accommodate their English proficiency differences.

EFL teachers also encounter several constraints during CBA implementation. These predominantly include insufficient time, students' focus on grades, lack of students' involvement, and the dominance of the teaching-to-the-test culture. Furthermore, additional challenges, based on the interview data analysis, include students' unfamiliarity with the informal CBA activities and syllabus overload. Some of these constraints confirm Ghaicha and Omarkly's (2018) alternative assessment constraints, namely, large class size and syllabus design. Added to these constraints is the inadequacy of the content covered in teacher education and training programs (Babni, 2019; Ghaicha & Omarkaly, 2018; Ghaicha & Oufela, 2021). Therefore, addressing these considerations and constraints is imperative for enhancing the quality of CBA practices.

4.2 Assessment Literacy (AL)

The second research question explores the extent to which teachers' AL contributes to the enhancement of their CBA practices. It has transpired that a significant proportion of EFL teachers lack formal assessment training, with many having never participated in any specific assessment training. The participants who received training, however, took courses where assessment and testing were covered as one element of that course.

As for the findings from the semi-structured interviews, the majority of EFL teachers who received pre-service training confirmed that it was primarily focused on test design and administration. Given this limited exposure to assessment in pre-service training, EFL teachers' assessment literacy is compromised, as evidenced by the present findings and those from Benzehaf (2017). As practicing professionals, most EFL teachers stated that they develop their assessment knowledge and skills by experimenting with CBA procedures in their classes, while others read relevant literature to update their assessment knowledge.

However, only some EFL teachers have had opportunities to participate in meetings or workshops conducted by their supervisors, indicating limited CPD opportunities for EFL teachers. Additionally, a large number of EFL teachers expressed a need for more comprehensive training in assessment, particularly in alternative assessment procedures, geared toward formative purposes. This confirms the findings put forth by Ghaicha and Omarkly (2018), who reported that some EFL teachers have never received any professional training in alternative assessment, highlighting the widespread desire among teachers to receive more training in the form of workshops, demo lessons and seminars.

5. Conclusion

The present study suggests several recommendations and implications at various levels. At the institutional level, a revision of teacher training programs and CPD, along with a rethinking of the place of assessment within these programs, is a required procedure. Additionally, the National Ministry of Education can contribute to the improvement of CBA by developing a clear and user-friendly guidebook delineating different CBA procedures and their formative functions for EFL teachers. Induction programs encompassing regular CPD activities, seminars and workshops, and self-paced online courses represent a practical and long-term solution to accompany teachers throughout their learning journey.

At the pedagogical level, students' involvement in CBA purposes and procedures is crucial to guarantee assessment effectiveness. Training students on the use and implementation of various assessment tools and on how to deal with feedback is also crucial. It is also necessary to encourage teachers to integrate performance-based assessment with clear criteria, linked to specific and measurable objectives. As for language skills, speaking and listening need to receive adequate coverage within CBA and be approached from an integrative perspective. The implementation of these recommendations crucially depends on the establishment of a coherent institutional framework.

Based on the findings of this study, future research directions could include investigating the underlying factors contributing to the variability in CBA practices among EFL teachers. Their approach to language assessment, together with the ways they view language and language learning, would contribute much to understanding the reasons why language skills and components are dealt with separately and with varying degrees of emphasis. Furthermore, examining students' perspectives and involvement in CBA planning, activities, and decision-making processes would reveal various insights on how to address this issue in practice.

Teacher training programs, as evidenced by the findings, still need revision and reconceptualization. Conducting a holistic evaluation of all training programs with an emphasis on the place of assessment is, in this respect, another future research direction. Investigating the impact of pre-service training programs on EFL teachers' competence in CBA is essential for enhancing teacher preparation in this area. Additionally, exploring teachers' and students' perceptions of CBA remains a lens through which training could be understood and approached.

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References

- Babni, A. (2019). Alternative assessment and English language teaching and learning in Morocco: High school teachers' perceptions and favourite methods and techniques. *Massalek Atarbiya wa Atakwine*, 2(2). 38-47 <https://doi.org/10.48403/IMIST.PRSM/massalek-v2i2.20171>
- Bailey, A. L., & Durán, R. (2019). A Mediator of valid interpretations of information generated by classroom assessments among linguistically and culturally diverse students. In S. M. Brookhart & J. H. McMillan (Eds.), *Classroom assessment and educational measurement* (pp. 46-62). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429507533-4>
- Benzehaf, B. (2017). Exploring teachers' assessment practices and skills. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 4(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.21449/ijate.254581>
- Bouziane, A. (2017). Why should the assessment of literacy in Morocco be revisited? In S. Hidri & C. Coombe (Eds.), *Evaluation in foreign language education in the Middle East and North Africa*, (pp. 305-314). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-43234-2_18
- Bowen, G. A. (2009), Document analysis as a qualitative research method, *Qualitative Research Journal*, 9(2), 27-40. <https://doi.org/10.3316/QRJ0902027>
- Broadfoot, P. M., Osborn, M. J., Sharpe, K., & Planel, C. D. (2001). Pupil assessment and classroom culture: A comparative study of the language of assessment in England and France. In D. Scott (Ed.), *Curriculum and Assessment* (Vol. 1, pp. 41 - 63). Ablex Publishing. <http://site.ebrary.com/id/10001988>

- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Dörnyei Zoltán. (2007). *Research methods in applied linguistics: Quantitative qualitative and mixed methodologies*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.4000/asp.294>
- Fulcher, G. (2012). Assessment literacy for the language classroom. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 9(2), 113–132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434303.2011.642041>
- Ghaicha, A., & Omarkaly, E. (2018). Alternative assessment in the Moroccan EFL classrooms teachers' conceptions and practices. *Higher Education of Social Science*, 14(1), 56 - 68. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3968/10161>
- Ghaicha, A. (2016). Theoretical framework for educational assessment: A synoptic review. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(24), 212-231.
- Ghaicha, A., & Oufela, Y. (2021). Moroccan EFL secondary school teachers' current practices and challenges of formative assessment. *Canadian Social Science*, 17(1), 1-15. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3968/12015>
- Hakim, B. (2015). English language teachers' ideology of ELT assessment literacy. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 3(4), 42-48. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.3n.4p.42>
- Hamp-Lyons, L. (2007). The Impact of testing practices on teaching: Ideologies and alternatives. In J. Cummins, C. Davison (Eds.), *International handbook of English language teaching*, (pp.487-504). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-46301-8_35
- Inbar-Lourie, O. (2017). Language Assessment Literacy. In E. Shohamy, I. Or, & S. May (Eds), *Language testing and assessment. Encyclopedia of language and education*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-02261-1_19
- Lewkowicz, J., & Leung, C. (2021). Classroom-based assessment. *Language Teaching*, 54(1), 47–57. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444820000506>
- Mamad, A., & Vigh, T. (2021). Moroccan EFL public high school teachers' perceptions and self-reported practices of assessment. *Journal of Language and Education*, 7(3), 119-135. <https://doi.org/10.17323/jle.2021.12067>
- McMillan, J. (2013). Why we need research on classroom assessment. In J. H. McMillan (Ed.), *SAGE handbook of research on classroom assessment* (pp. 2-16). SAGE Publications. <https://www.doi.org/10.4135/9781452218649.n1>

- Ouakrime, M. (2000). An argument for a more formative approach to assessment in ELT in Morocco. In *Proceedings of the 20th MATE Annual Conference* (pp. 97-107). Moroccan Association of Teachers of English.
- Kane, M. T., & Wools, S. (2019). Perspectives on the validity of classroom assessments. In S. M. Brookhart & J. H. McMillan (Eds.), *Classroom assessment and educational measurement* (pp. 11-26). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429507533-2>
- Randel, B., & Clark, T. (2013). Measuring classroom assessment practices. In J. H. McMillan (Ed.), *SAGE handbook of research on classroom assessment* (pp. 145-163). SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452218649.n9>
- Rodriguez, M. C., & Haladyna, T. M. (2013). Writing selected-response items for classroom. In J. H. McMillan (Ed.), *SAGE handbook of research on classroom assessment* (pp. 293-312). SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452218649.n17>
- Shohamy, E. (2017). Critical language testing. In E. Shohamy, I. Or, & S. May (Eds), *Language testing and assessment. Encyclopedia of language and education* (3rd ed., pp. 441-454). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-02261-1_26
- Stoynoff, S. (2012). Looking backward and forward at classroom-based language assessment. *ELT Journal*, 66(4), 523-532. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccs041>
- Turner, C. E. (2012). Classroom assessment. In G. Fulcher & F. Davidson (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of language testing* (pp. 65-78). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203181287-12>
- World Bank Group. (2015). *Belarus student assessment: SABER country report 2015*. Systems Approach for Better Education Results. World Bank. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/26537>